

HILBERT SPACES

¹ Smt. Sheeba Jeyaseeli .M, ² Shri.M.Karthigeyan, M.Sc., M.Phil., B.Ed.,

¹M.phil Research scholar, ² Assistant Professor,

^{1,2} Department of Mathematics,

^{1,2} PonnaiyahRamajayam Institute of Science and Technology,

^{1,2} PRIST Deemed to be University,

¹ samuelrajcumara@gmail.com, ² karthigeyan356@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Infinite-dimensional systems are widely used to represent many phenomena in the real-world such as properties of elastic material, fluid dynamics, heat conduction, reaction-diffusion processes, etc. A study of the parameters like concentration, temperature, velocity, displacement, etc., are commonly assigned as a state variable. In particular, a dynamical system has the plant equation as Partial Differential Equation (PDE), functional differential equation, Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE), or an abstract evolution equation. Moreover, SDEs are the generalization of deterministic differential equations involving noise term, and it is useful in many applications like economic dynamics, i.e., anyone needs to manage occasions like corporate defaults, operational disappointments or insured accidents.

Keywords : PDE, SDE, HILBERT SPACES.

INTRODUCTION

In general, a stochastic dynamical system is also requires more than one noise like Brownian motion and Poisson process to frame its dynamics [1]. Stochastic calculus concerning fractional Brownian motion (fBm) has gained considerable popularity and it is a group of centered Gaussian processes with continuous sample paths indexed by Hurst parameter $H \in (0, 1)$. fBm reduces to standard Brownian motion when $H = 1$. From the application viewpoint, limitation on Gaussian noise is unsuitable to model and consequently to deal these situations, one can exchange Gaussian noise by Poisson random measure. For instance, the model of river

pollution is studied by Hausenblas and Marchis [2], in which the number of deposits on a bounded region of the river at infinitesimal length is $d\eta$, where η is the distance coordinate along the river that behaves according to the Poisson process.

The Optimal Control Problem (OCP) describes a path of control variables concerned with minimizing the cost functional or maximizing the payoff to the corresponding dynamical system under the set of admissible control functions. The reason for studying OCPs in Hilbert space has the merit of giving a measure of unification for a wide range of problems and providing fruitful applications in many domains of science and engineering [3]. Notably, the control problems having the continuous parameter dynamical system where the state dynamics are represented by PDE/Stochastic PDE (SPDE) are conveniently established in this way.

Further, the models of fractional systems attain a lot of importance because of their excellent and powerful tools to depict memory and hereditary properties of different processes in diverse fields of science and engineering (see [4,5]). The fractional derivatives give a phenomenal instrument for describing memory and method of genetic properties of different materials, which is a significant advantage of fractional calculus. Recently, Fractional Differential Equations (FDEs) appear in the fields of electro expository science, visco-flexibility, fragmentary multi-poles, electrical circuits and neuron demonstrating a unique ramification of material and organic sciences [6]. Hilfer [7] introduced a common fractional derivative operator known as Hilfer Fractional Derivative (HFD), that is the combination of

Riemann-Liouville and Caputo fractional derivatives. HFD is carried out in hypothetical simulation of dielectric unwinding in glass shaping substances [8]. Since variables in the financial system have long memories, the fractional order system is suitable for studying the behavior in economic systems [9].

A multi-valued dynamical system with HFD plays a substantial role in the investigation of different dynamical processes and phenomena represented by a discontinuous equation which arises in the inquiry of economic dynamics, Coulomb friction dynamical problems and biological systems [10].

Nowadays, contact between deformable bodies is well developed. For instance, tires on roads, brake pads in contact with wheels and pistons with skirts. On the account of the significance of contact processes in mechanical systems, substantial hard work is placed into their numerical simulations, modeling and analysis. Hemivariational inequalities were first proposed by Panagiotopoulos [11], which represents a class of nonlinear inclusions that are associated with Clarke's sub-differential operator, and have applications in non-convex optimization and structural analysis. Clarke's sub-differential type is used to describe the frictional contact problem in mechanics, and have applications in non-smooth analysis and optimization. The semigroup theory of bounded linear operators is firmly identified to find solvability of Abstract Differential Equations (ADEs) within infinite-dimensional spaces [12]. By using an infinitesimal generator A of C_0 -semigroup of bounded linear operators $T(t)$ on Hilbert space, one can construct a mild solution (the solution which is defined in the domain of the infinitesimal generator A) including some properties of stochastic analysis and fractional calculus. Fixed point theory is a fruitful tool in present mathematics, and it plays a substantial role in nonlinear analysis. Two important approaches to the solution of nonlinear equations are described as topological and variational. Topological methods are obtained from fixed

point theorems and are usually based on the idea of the topological degree. Variational methods represent the solutions as critical points of a suitable functional and find some ways of locating them. The fixed point method is regarded as a potent and essential tool to study the existence of a solution. Finding a solution of major problems in abstract space, a fixed point approach is a better way since it is advantageous, and delivers suitable convergence theory. The fixed point techniques have broad application in theoretical as well as numerical aspects and extensively applied to the field of the stochastic control system. The dynamical system contains a Poisson process, and the mild solution to the system is not a continuous stochastic process, but this process has càdlàg path. Hence, for solvability, the complete continuity condition has no meaning in the presence of a jump term. To overcome this complexity, we have to decompose the solution operator to satisfy a suitable Fixed Point Theorem (FPT), and an obtained fixed point is a mild solution of a proposed control problem. There have been minimal works done in the stochastic optimal control of FDE/fractional differential inclusion in the presence of Clarke's sub-differential [13].

Basic Concepts and Definitions

Definition 1.1.[14] A vector space over a field F is the set V combined with two operations $+$ and $\cdot$ called vector addition and scalar multiplication should satisfy the following conditions:

If a and b are any vectors in V , then $a + b \in V$.

(1) For every vectors a and b in V , $a + b = b + a$.

(2) The vectors a, b, f in V , $a + (b + f) = (a + b) + f$.

(3) The set V contains an additive identity element, denoted by 0 , such that for any vector $a \in V$, $0 + a = a$ and $a + 0 = a$.

(4) Every vector $a \in V$, the equations $a + i = 0$ and $i + a = 0$ with $i \in V$, known as additive inverse of a and represented by $-a$.

The operation $\cdot$ (scalar multiplication) is represented between real numbers (or scalars) and vectors, it satisfies the following conditions: If a is any vector in V , and $c \in \mathbf{F}$, then the product $c \cdot a \in V$.

$$(5) \text{ For } c \in \mathbf{F} \text{ and all vectors } a, b \in V, c \cdot (a+b) = c \cdot a + c \cdot b$$

$$(6) \text{ For } c, d \in \mathbf{F} \text{ and all vectors } a \in V, (c+d) \cdot a = c \cdot a + d \cdot a$$

$$(7) \text{ For } c, d \in \mathbf{F} \text{ and all vectors } a \in V, c \cdot (d \cdot a) = (cd) \cdot a$$

$$(8) \text{ For each vector } a \in V, 1 \cdot a = a.$$

Definition 1.2. [15] Let V be a vector space over $\mathbf{F}$. A norm defined on V is a function

$\|\cdot\|$ from V to $\mathbf{F}$ such that, for every $u, v \in V$ and $\alpha \in \mathbf{F}$,

$$(1) \|u\| \geq 0 \text{ and } \|u\| = 0 \text{ if and only if } u = 0,$$

$$(2) \|u+v\| \leq \|u\| + \|v\|,$$

$$(3) \|\alpha u\| = |\alpha| \|u\|.$$

A **normed linear space** is a vector space induced with the norm.

Definition 1.3. [16] A complete normed space over the field $\mathbf{F}$ is called as a **Banach space**.

Example 1.1. [17] Are all linear spaces a Banach space under the norm $\|x\| = |x|$.

Definition 1.4. [18] Let X be a Banach space. The mapping $J : X \rightarrow X^*$ is called the natural imbedding or canonical mapping of X into X^* . If the mapping J is onto, then X is **reflexive Banach space**.

Definition 1.5. [19] Let X be the linear space over the field $\mathbf{F}$ where $\mathbf{F}$ is either the field of real numbers or the field of complex numbers and an inner product on X is a mapping from $X \times X$ into $\mathbf{F}$ which assigns to each ordered pair of vectors (x, y) in X such that,

Definition 1.6. [20] Let H be a complex Banach space then H is called the **Hilbert space** if the complex number x, y is the inner product of x and y is associated with the norm induced by the inner product.

Example 1.2. [21] Consider $L_2[0, 1]$ be the set of all square integrable function on $[0, 1]$.

Definition 1.7. [20] A set $E \subset \mathbf{R}^n$ is a **convex set** if for each pair of points $x, y \in E$, the entire line segment joining these two points is also in E , i.e.,

$$\lambda x + (1-\lambda)y \in E, \quad \text{for all } \lambda \in [0, 1].$$

If the set is not convex, then it is called **concave set**.

Definition 1.8. [20] A real valued function f defined on a convex set $E \subset \mathbf{R}^n$ is **convex function**, if for each pair of points $x, y \in E$ and for all $\lambda \in [0, 1]$,

$$f(\lambda x + (1-\lambda)y) \leq \lambda f(x) + (1-\lambda)f(y).$$

If for each pair of points $x, y \in E$ and for all $\lambda \in [0, 1]$,

$$f(\lambda x + (1-\lambda)y) \geq \lambda f(x) + (1-\lambda)f(y),$$

then f is called **concave function**.

Definition 1.9. Let X be a Banach space. A subset S of X is said to be **dense** in X if the closure of S , $\bar{S} = X$. A Banach space X is called **separable** if it contains a countable dense subset.

Definition 1.10. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ is said to **converge** in the metric space (X, d) , if for every $\epsilon > 0$ there exist some integer n_0 such that $d(x_n, x) < \epsilon$, with $x \in X$ and for every $n \geq n_0$.

Definition 1.11. Let d be a metric on a non-empty set X . A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X is said to be **Cauchy sequence**, if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists some integer n_0 such that $d(x_n, x_m) < \epsilon$, for every $n, m \geq n_0$. The metric space (X, d) is said to be **complete**, if every Cauchy sequence in X converges.

Definition 1.12. Let Y and Z be metric spaces with metrics d and e respectively, then $f: Y \rightarrow Z$ is said to be **continuous** at a point $x_0 \in Y$ if for every $\epsilon > 0$, there exists a $\delta > 0$ (possibly depending on ϵ and x_0) such that $\|f(x) - f(x_0)\|_e < \epsilon$ for all $x \in Y$ satisfying $\|x - x_0\|_d < \delta$.

Further, f is discontinuous on Y if it is continuous at every point of Y .

Definition 1.13. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in $C[a, b]$ is said to be **equicontinuous**, if for every

$\epsilon > 0$ there is a $\delta > 0$, depending only on ϵ , such that for all x_n and $s_1, s_2 \in [a, b]$ satisfying

$$|s_1 - s_2| < \delta \text{ we have } |x_n(s_1) - x_n(s_2)| < \epsilon.$$

Definition 1.14. Let X and Y be vector spaces over

$\mathbb{F}$. A **linear map** from X to Y is a function $F: X \rightarrow Y$ such that

$$F(k_1x_1 + k_2x_2) = k_1F(x_1) + k_2F(x_2),$$

for all $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{F}$.

Definition 1.15. Let X and Y be norm linear spaces and $F: D(F) \rightarrow Y$ a

linear operator, where $D(F) \subset X$. F is **bounded**, if there is a real number c such that for all $a \in D(F)$, $\|F(a)\| \leq c\|a\|$.

Moreover, F is called a **compact linear operator**, if F is linear and if for every bounded subset X of X , the image $F(X)$ is **relatively compact**, that is, the closure of $F(X)$ is compact.

Definition 1.16. Let X, Y be Banach spaces and $T: D \subset X \rightarrow Y$ be an operator.

(1) The operator T is said to be **bounded**, if it maps any bounded subset of D into a bounded subset of Y .

(2) The operator T is said to be **completely continuous**, if it is continuous and maps any bounded subset of D into a relatively compact subset of Y . In other words, continuous operator $T: D \subset X \rightarrow Y$ is completely continuous if and only if for every bounded sequence (a_k) with every $a_k \in D$, the sequence $(T(a_k))$ has a convergent subsequence.

Remark 1.1. (1) In Hilbert space, any completely continuous operator is a bounded operator.

(2) Compact operators are always completely continuous, but completely continuous operators may be non-compact. In reflexive spaces, completely continuous operators are compact.

Definition 1.17. Let X be a topological space. Let x_0 be a point in X and $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty, \infty\}$ is an extended real valued function. We say that f is lower semi-continuous (l.s.c) at x_0 , if for every $y < f(x_0)$ there exists a neighborhood V of x_0 such that $f(x) > y$ for all $x \in V$. The function f is called **lower semi-continuous**, if it is lower semi-continuous at every point of its domain.

Definition 1.18. Let X and Y be non-empty sets. T is said to be a **multi-valued mapping** from X to Y if T is a function from X to the power set of Y . We denote a multi-valued map by $T: X \rightarrow 2^Y$.

Let X and Y be Banach spaces. Let $P(X)$ be the set of all non-empty subsets of X . Let

$$P_{cl}(X) = \{A \in P(X) : A \text{ is closed}\}, P_{bd}(X) = \{A \in P(X) : A \text{ is bounded}\},$$

$$P_{cp}(X) = \{A \in P(X) : A \text{ is compact}\} \text{ and } P_{cv}(X) = \{A \in P(X) : A \text{ is convex}\}.$$

Definition 1.19. Let X be a Banach space and denote the graph

$$hGr(F) = \{(x, y) \in$$

$$X \times Y : x \in X, y \in F(x)\}.$$

A multi-valued map is represented as $F: X \rightarrow 2^X \setminus \{0\} = P(X)$. Then

(i) If $F(x)$ is **convex** then F is convex valued for every $x \in X$.

(ii) F is said to be **upper semicontinuous** (u.s.c) on X , if for every $x_0 \in X$, the set $F(x_0)$ is non-empty, closed subset of X and if for each open set U of X containing $F(x_0)$, there exists an open neighborhood V of x_0 such that $F(V) \subset U$.

(iii) If $F(B) = \cup_{x \in B} F(x)$ is **bounded** in X for all $B \in P_{bd}(X)$, then F is a bounded set (i.e. $\sup_{x \in B} \{\sup\{\|y\| : y \in F(x)\}\} < \infty$).

(iv) F maps bounded sets into relatively compact then F is **completely continuous**, for every $B \in P(X)$.

(v) If the graph $Gr(F)$ is a closed subset of $X \times Y$, then the

ulti-valued map F is closed.

(vi) *Has a fixed point if there is an element $x \in X$ such that $ax \in F(x)$.*

CONCLUSION

This research develops an optimal control of stochastic PDEs. The first section deals with a nonlinear delay fractional reaction-diffusion equations governed by Poisson jumps in Hilbert space. By constructing a suitable MNC, the existence of mild solution for the proposed problem is proved through FPT of condensing maps and fractional calculus. Moreover, the existence of optimal control is proved by employing Balder's theorem. An example of a fractional control problem with Poisson jumps is given to confirm the developed results. The second section provides a study of time-fractional stochastic Ginzburg-Landau equation with mixed fBm in Hilbert space involving fractional Laplacian. Solvability of the proposed SPDE model is discussed by using Mittag-Leffler functions, stochastic analysis and Krasnoselskii's FPT. Further, optimal control is established by employing Balder's theorem and Gronwall's inequality for the proposed system. An example is provided for the developed theoretical results.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Norden E. Huang, Zheng Shen, Steven R. Long, Manli C. Wu, Hsing H. Shih, Quanan Zheng, Nai-Chyuan Yen, Chi Chao Tung and Henry H. Liu, "The empirical mode decomposition and the Hilbert spectrum for nonlinear and non-stationary time series analyses", The Royal Society, Printed in Great Britain, (1998) 454, 903-995.
- [2]. GANG WANG, XIAN-YAO CHEN and FANG-LI QIAO, " ON INTRINSIC MODE FUNCTION ", Presented at the World Scientific Publishing Company, Vol. 2, No. 3 (2010) 277–293.
- [3]. Aditi Singh, "Survey Paper on Hilbert Transform with Its Applications in Signal Processing", (IJCSIT) International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies, Vol. 5 (3), 2014, 3880-3882.
- [4]. Jianping Hu, Xiaochao Wang, Hong Qin, "Novel and efficient computation of Hilbert–Huang transform on surfaces", Computer Aided Geometric Design, 2016, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cagd.2016.02.011>.
- [5]. Norden E. Huang and Zhaohua Wu, (2008), "A review on Hilbert–Huang transform: method and its applications to geophysical studies", Rev. Geophysical, 46, RG2006, doi:10.1029/2007RG000228.
- [6]. Mans Klingspor, "Hilbert transform: Mathematical theory and applications to signal processing", the Linkoping University, LiTH - MAT EX, November 19, 2015.
- [7]. Yi-Wen Liu, (2012), "Hilbert Transform and Applications, Fourier Transform Applications, Dr. Salih. Salih", Taiwan's National Science Council through research grant, No. 100-2221-E-007-011.